

Type of Work: Registered Report

Nasalization in Korebaju: An Evaluation of Reproducibility in Laboratory Phonology and Phonetic Fieldwork

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Abstract

This study examines nasalization in Korebaju (also known as Koreguahe or Koreguaje), a Tukanoan language spoken in Colombia, from the perspective of reproducibility in Laboratory Phonology and phonetic fieldwork. The main aim is to investigate inferential replicability (“Type E reproducibility”, following the classification proposed by Simkus 2025) by applying laboratory and statistical methods to re-evaluate the phonological analysis of nasal harmony in Korebaju. This analysis concerns issues such as directionality, target segments, blockers, and transparent segments, originally described in earlier phonological work on Korebaju (Dupont 1988; Cook and Criswell 1993; Dupont 2021), whose analyses relied primarily on qualitative and impressionistic observations conducted more than three decades ago.

To address this question, the study presents two experiments designed to examine different aspects of reproducibility. In the first experiment, we test Type E reproducibility by collecting two datasets from a single speaker using comparable stimuli but two different phonetic instruments, each employing a distinct method for capturing nasal airflow data: the EVA2, which uses nasal tubes, and the EGG-D800, which uses a silicone mask. The study evaluates whether these distinct instruments lead to comparable conclusions despite the different nature of the data produced.

In a second experiment, we test Type C reproducibility by using the same stimuli and instrument (EGG-D800) with two speakers of similar age and gender recorded under different environmental conditions: one in a phonetics laboratory in France and the other in a Korebaju village in the Colombian Amazon.

In all experiments, the nasalization index used in the original study was maintained, calculating the proportion of nasal airflow. The same statistical procedures were applied to each dataset individually in order to evaluate their comparability and their

ability to corroborate the phonological hypotheses concerning phonetic differences between nasal and nasalized vowels, as well as between nasal, nasalized, opaque, and transparent consonants.

The findings provide evidence for the robustness of nasalization indices and for the relative equivalence, from a phonological perspective, of data obtained using different instruments and under distinct environmental conditions. The study also contributes to the phonetic and phonological understanding of nasalization phenomena in Korebaju, particularly with respect to vowel nasalization, the distribution of nasal airflow in the language's phonotactics and syllable structure, and the behavior of transparent segments.

1. Introduction

1.1. Production and Aerodynamics of Nasal Sounds

1.1.1. Velopharyngeal Function and Nasalization

Vega et al. (2024) state that nasal sounds occur when the velum lowers, opening the velopharyngeal port and allowing airflow from the lungs to pass through the larynx, pharynx, and nasal cavity. Both nasal consonants and vowels involve oral articulation, with varying degrees of oral closure and vocal fold vibration as the sound source. The opening of the velopharyngeal port while the oral cavity remains partially closed enables resonance through the nasal passages (Ladefoged & Maddieson, 1996; Stevens, 1998).

Vega et al (2024) also note that studies using the pressure-flow method (Warren & DuBois, 1964; Shosted, 2011) and other aerodynamic measurements (Benguereel et al., 1975; Lubker & Moll, 1965) indicate that different oral articulations influence nasal airflow, with velar sounds producing greater nasal airflow than bilabials. Subsequent research confirms that nasal airflow depends on both velum movement and oral articulation (Thompson & Hixon, 1979; Texeira et al., 2000; Basset et al., 2001; Delvaux et al., 2008; Chi et al., 2015), while lower nasal vowels are produced with reduced velum displacement (Shosted, 2011; Hajek, 1997). Velum movement typically occurs at approximately 5 Hz (less than 200–300 ms), which is relatively slow compared to the movements of other articulators such as the tongue, lips, or jaw. This slower movement facilitates the propagation of nasal sounds during production (Stevens, 1998).

Nasal coarticulation, the influence of nasal segments on adjacent sounds, has been widely studied and varies across languages (Basset et al., 2001; Delvaux et al., 2008; Passavant, 1863; Solé, 1995, 2007; Ohala, 1971, 1975; Clumeck, 1976). Recent studies propose a continuum of nasality based on the degree of velopharyngeal opening, ranging from oral segments with velum closure to nasal vowels and consonants (De Boer et al., 2023). Another notable phenomenon is nasal consonants with oral release at the end, observed in some African languages, which help limit the spread of nasality to the following vowel by reducing nasal airflow at the consonant's release (Ladefoged & Maddieson, 1996; Anderson, 1976; Wetzels & Nevins, 2018; Demolin et al., 2006). A particularly common phenomenon among Amazonian

languages is *rhinoglottophilia*, that is, the nasalization of vowels adjacent to [h], as in Baniwa, an Arawakan language from Northwest Amazonia, where a word such as /oho/ 'yes' is regularly produced as [ʰõhõ] (Matisoff, 1975; Chacon & Carvalho, 2020). Vega et al. (2024) emphasize that these aerodynamic and articulatory patterns are crucial for understanding nasality in Korebaju, highlighting both segmental and suprasegmental interactions in vowel and consonant production.

1.1.2. Aerodynamic Studies in Amerindian and Tukanoan Languages

Few studies have examined nasality from an aerodynamic perspective. In Karitiana, an isolated indigenous language from Brazil, a post-stopped nasal allophone (e.g., [mb]) is characterized by increased intraoral pressure and nasal airflow, illustrating contrasts between nasal segments (Demolin, Haude, & Storto, 2006). Research on Kakataibo in Peru shows nasal coarticulation near nasal vowels, with effects modulated by process directionality, stress, syllable boundaries, and prosody (Avelino, Zariquiey, & Pérez-Silva, 2020). In Tukanoan languages, including Korebaju, phonetic studies are limited; in Siona, a Western Tukanoan language, velum movement during nasal and oral productions was measured using the earbuds method, revealing progressive and regressive nasal harmonies influenced by suffixes (Bruil & Stewart, 2022). Anticipatory and carry-over nasal coarticulation has also been documented at the phonological level across Western and Eastern Tukanoan languages (Sylak-Glassman, Farmer, & Michael, 2014; Stenzel, 2007, 2013; de L. Silva, 2012; Gómez-Imbert, 2003, 2004; Kaye, 1971).

1.1.3. The Korebaju Language

According to Vega et al. (2024), Korebaju (autonym [kòrèβàhí], also known as Koreguaje; ISO 639-3: coe; Glottocode: core1283) is a language of the Western Tukanoan family spoken in the Colombian Amazon along the Orteguzza, Peneya, Consaya, and Caquetá rivers, with approximately 2,000 speakers (Korebaju Community, 2011; Moseley, 2010). The contemporary Korebaju-speaking community emerged from the historical union of four populations, Korebaju, Tama, Macaguaje, and Carijona, who adopted Korebaju as their main language. This process led to the extinction of their original languages, although some cultural practices have been preserved. Dialectal variation exists as communities settled in distinct territories and maintain clan-based distinctions that reinforce group identity (Gralow, 1985; Chacón, 2016).

Previous descriptions of Korebaju phonology have noted features such as tone, nasal harmony, and glottalization (Young et al., 1984; Dupont, 1988; Cook & Criswell, 1993; Cook & Gralow, 2001; Dupont, 2021; Vega, 2019; Vega & Vallée, 2021), but detailed phonetic and acoustic and spectrographic data remain limited. Notably, since 2017, a consistent observation has been made that most nasal consonants in Korebaju exhibit a burst at the end of production. This phenomenon was initially hypothesized to result from modifications in the glottal cycle but was later rejected following further analysis (Vega, 2019; Vega & Vallée, 2021). The Korebaju vowel inventory includes six oral vowels /i, e, a, o, u, i/, six nasal vowels /ĩ, ě, ã, õ, ũ, ỹ/, three glottal vowels /aʔ, eʔ, oʔ/, seventeen consonants /p, t, k, pʰ, tʰ, kʰ, β, φ, s, h, w, c, m, n, ɲ, hɲ, r/, and a system of segmental and suprasegmental glottalization. The Tama and Korebaju dialects differ prosodically and, in the production, and distribution of glottalization. Communities are located about one hour apart by canoe but share cultural events, educational

institutions, and organizational activities, including a boarding school within the Korebaju reserve (Vega et al., 2024).

The previous analyses are grounded in the nasal harmony hypothesis formulated by Dupont (1988) and later revisited in Dupont (2021). Within this framework, nasality is treated as a suprasegmental feature associated with the vowel of the first syllable of the morpheme and capable of spreading across segments within the morphological domain.

The phonological description of Korebaju presented by Cook and Criswell (1993) explicitly draws on Dupont's proposal, as acknowledged by the authors. However, their description presents the blocking behavior in terms of specific segments, identifying bilabial, alveolar and velar stops, as well as /r/ and /s/, as elements that stop the propagation of nasalization. Dupont's analysis, in contrast, formulates the blocking mechanism in terms of phonological classes, particularly voiceless obstruents, and later work (Dupont 2021) also highlights the role of the glottal stop /ʔ/ as a strong blocker.

In the present study, Dupont's framework is adopted as the primary phonological reference for interpreting nasal spreading in Korebaju.

In the phonological system of Korebaju, nasality plays a central role as a suprasegmental phenomenon. Following Dupont's analysis, this feature is associated with the vocalic nucleus of the first syllable of a morpheme, from which it may extend to other segments within the same morphological domain. This spreading process, governed by formal rules that determine the environments in which propagation is possible or blocked, affects both vowels and certain adjacent consonants and results in fully nasalized morphological forms as well as allomorphic alternations (Dupont 2021: 353–354).

Nasality is therefore represented phonologically not as a property of individual segments but as a suprasegmental [+nasal] feature that can spread across segments. This spreading results in the nasal realization of segments that are underlyingly oral. However, the propagation of the nasal feature may be blocked by certain segments, particularly voiceless stops and, most notably, the glottal stop /ʔ/, which prevents the continuation of nasal spreading (Dupont 2021: 360).

At the morphological level, nasal harmony also gives rise to allomorphic variation depending on whether the root is nasal or oral. The alternation of the verbal suffix illustrates what Dupont (1988: 114) describes as the notion of virtuality in Korebaju morphology. The suffix appears as {-tʃe} after oral roots and as {-ne} after nasal roots when the root contains a nasalized vowel. This alternation demonstrates the direct influence of suprasegmental nasality on morphological derivation (Dupont 2021: 360–361).

As illustrated in the autosegmental representation provided below (Figure 1), the [+nasal] feature associated with the vowel of the first syllable of the morpheme spreads to adjacent segments within the morphological domain until it encounters a blocking segment. In this analysis, nasality is treated as a lexically relevant feature of morphemes that surfaces according to structured rules of spreading and blocking. This framework provides an efficient account of the Korebaju phonological system while

integrating its morphological and phonological processes with those attested in other languages of the same family (Dupont 2021: 365).

Figure 1. Autosegmental representation of bidirectional nasal spreading in Korebaju (/bɥo+tʃo/ → [mɥo+nɔ]) ‘finger’ (adapted from Dupont 1988: 112-113).

2. Objectives and Hypotheses

2.1. Objectives

Following the taxonomy of reproducibility proposed by Simkus (2025), this study focuses primarily on Type E and Type C reproducibility.

- To evaluate nasalization in nasal and nasalized vowels in Korebaju using a nasal airflow index defined as the proportion of nasal airflow relative to the sum of nasal and oral airflow (NAF/(NAF+OAF)), following the procedure used in Vega Rodriguez et al. (2024).
- To compare data obtained using different phonetic instruments (EVA2, EGG-D800, and microphone) in order to examine how different data-collection methods affect the measurement of nasal airflow.
- To test Type E reproducibility (Simkus 2025) by examining whether datasets collected from the same speaker using different phonetic instruments lead to the same conclusions regarding phonetic differences between nasal and nasalized vowels.
- To test Type C **reproducibility** by comparing data collected from different speakers recorded in different environments (a phonetics laboratory and a Korebaju village in the Colombian Amazon) using the same experimental design.
- To evaluate whether the experimental results provide empirical support for the phonological analysis of nasal harmony in Korebaju proposed by Dupont (1988) and further discussed in Dupont (2021), particularly regarding the directionality of nasal spreading, the segments affected by the process, and the role of blocking and transparent segments.

2.2. Hypotheses

H1. Oral, nasal, and nasalized vowels in Korebaju are expected to differ systematically in the proportion of nasal airflow measured during speech production.

2.3. Research Questions

RQ1. Do datasets obtained with different phonetic instruments (EVA2 intranasal tubes vs. EGG-D800 silicone mask) lead to comparable conclusions regarding the phonetic distinction between nasal and nasalized vowels?

RQ2. Do datasets collected from different speakers and recording environments yield statistically consistent patterns in the identification of phonetic

RQ3. Do the experimental results provide empirical support for the phonological analysis of nasal harmony proposed by Dupont (1988, 2021), particularly with respect to directionality, target segments, blocking segments, and transparent segments?

3. Description of the datasets

The datasets analyzed in the present study were collected prior to the present submission as part of previous phonetic fieldwork conducted in 2021 and 2023. The aim of this Stage 1 Registered Report is therefore not to collect new data, but to preregister the analytical procedures used to examine these existing datasets within a reproducibility-oriented framework. As shown in Table 1, the study draws on three corpora recorded in two locations, France and Agua Negra, using two phonetic instruments, EVA and EGG-D800.

Table 1. Corpora

Instrument	Stimuli	Location	Date	Participant
EVA	Wordlist A	France	2023	Participant-A
EGG-D800	Wordlist B	Agua Negra	2021	Participant-A +11 participants
	Wordlist C	Agua Negra	2023	Participant-A +5 participants (subset of 11 above)

Following the PCI Registered Reports taxonomy for studies involving pre-existing data, the present submission corresponds to **Level 1 bias control**, since the authors had prior access to the datasets and portions of these recordings have been used in previous work, including the analysis of nasal airflow during speech production in Korebaju reported by Vega Rodriguez et al. (2024). However, the analyses proposed in the present preregistered protocol address a different research objective, namely

the evaluation of reproducibility across datasets, instruments, speakers, and recording environments. These specific analyses have not yet been conducted. To reduce potential hindsight bias and analytic flexibility, the present manuscript specifies in advance the datasets to be analyzed, the inclusion criteria, the dependent measures, the statistical models, and the interpretation criteria. Any analyses not included in the present preregistered plan will be explicitly labeled as exploratory in the final Stage 2 manuscript.

The recordings were originally collected as part of broader phonetic fieldwork on Korebaju, designed to investigate nasalization as well as other phonetic and phonological phenomena in the language, including tonal patterns and glottalization.

3.1 Corpus

Three corpora were used in this study, corresponding to the datasets summarized in Table 1. **Wordlist A** consists of 54 words produced in isolation and repeated three times in random order. This corpus covers all possible occurrences of nasal consonants within roots and morphemes, although the complete tonal inventory is not included due to ongoing research on the tonal system. Each word contains at least one nasal consonant, with target syllables including CV and NV structures in both word-initial and medial positions, as well as in certain affix morphemes. Words consist minimally of a bimoraic root morpheme, which takes the form of CVCV, CVV, or CVGV, where C can be oral or nasal, G a glottal sound /h/ or /ʔ/, and V can be a modal or a laryngealized vowel.

The second and third corpora consist of **Wordlist B and C**, containing 118 and 145 items and recorded between 2021 and 2023, respectively. Different from Wordlist A, in B and C, words were embedded within a carrier sentence. The first list of 118 words was collected from 12 speakers and was designed to elicit productions of minimal and quasi-minimal pairs across as many lexical contexts as possible. The second list, consisting of 145 words, was recorded from six speakers, three from each variety (say again their names), balanced for gender and generation, who had already participated in the initial 118-word survey. This second list aimed to complete the identification of minimal and quasi-minimal pairs in all possible contexts for each variety and to verify the presence of nasal harmony and tonal patterns.

The carrier sentence was constructed as follows:

/ci:kínà ìkámè ___ kóʔrèbàhí ció pí/
{ci:kínà iká-mè ___ kóʔrèbàhí ció pí}
we say-PL ___ Korebaju language
'We say ___ in Korebaju'

3.2 Participants

The 54-word corpus was recorded with a single participant, a 67-year-old native speaker of Korebaju. Before this study, she had never been away from her community for more than two weeks, and her stay in France marked her first prolonged absence, lasting 88 days. Spanish, acquired during her schooling, is her second language.

For the 118- and 145-word lists, twelve native speakers of Korebaju participated, evenly divided by sex with six males and six females, and representing two generations: G1, aged 18 to 31, and G2, aged 42 to 70. All participants were of Korebaju descent and used Spanish as a second language, both with local settlers and at the regional boarding secondary school. None had previously been away from the community for more than two weeks at the time of recording. Importantly, the 67-year-old participant from the 54-word corpus is included in this larger group and is the only individual who had spent an extended period outside the community, totaling 66 days. All twelve participants also took part in the recordings of the other two word lists.

3.3. Recording Procedure

The 54-word corpus and the 118-word list were recorded in France by the 67-year-old native speaker using the EVA system. The remaining two lists (118- and 145-word lists) were recorded in the Korebaju community (Agua Negra) with the eleven and six participants using electroglottography (EGG).

It is important to note that, for this study, only 18 of the 54 items in Corpus A will be analyzed. This selection was made based on their correspondence with items in Corpus B, ensuring comparability across datasets. By focusing on lexical items that are shared between both corpora, we aim to obtain reliable results derived from equivalent linguistic material recorded in both datasets.

3.3.1. Recording Instruments

The present study utilized advanced instrumentation to capture detailed acoustic, aerodynamic, and physiological data during speech production. Two primary systems were employed: the Assisted Vocal Evaluation (EVA2™) workstation and the Rothenberg OroNasal mask with electroglottography (EGG). These tools allow for precise measurement of airflow, subglottal pressure, glottal activity, and acoustic properties, providing a comprehensive view of the vocal production mechanisms that cannot be captured through auditory analysis alone.

The EVA2™ system integrates multiple data streams synchronously, including acoustic signals, oral and nasal airflow, and physiological parameters, enabling multiparametric analyses of voice production in both laboratory and field conditions. In parallel, the Rothenberg mask, in its original and OroNasal versions, has historically enabled reliable aerodynamic measurements while accounting for potential acoustic effects induced by the mask design. Together, these instruments form a robust methodological framework for investigating the phonetic and phonological properties of Korebaju speech, including nasalization, glottalization, and other segmental and suprasegmental features.

3.3.2. Assisted Vocal Evaluation (EVA2™)

The *Assisted Vocal Evaluation system (EVA2™)* (Figure 2) is an advanced workstation for measuring and analyzing the mechanisms of human voice production. Developed Ghio et al. (2022), it is designed to perform multiparametric voice analyses by integrating acoustic, aerodynamic, and physiological data in a synchronized manner (Ghio et al., 2022).

Technical Features

EVA2 allows simultaneous acquisition of multiple types of data:

- **Acoustic:** Intensity, fundamental frequency, and formant spectra, using external microphones and electroglottography (sampling at 25 kHz).
- **Aerodynamic:** Oral airflow (up to 10 L/s) and nasal airflow (up to 3 L/s), as well as intraoral and subglottal pressure (up to 100 hPa), sampled at 6.25 kHz.
- **Physiological:** Glottal activity recorded via electroglottography, and detection of velar and tongue movements.

All sensors are connected to a single analog-to-digital converter, allowing synchronized and multiplexed data acquisition, ensuring stable calibration and precise measurement.

Innovations and Advantages

EVA2 enables the capture of information that cannot be observed through acoustic sound alone, such as nasal airflow, subglottal pressure, and glottal movements. Its ability to integrate these data synchronously provides a comprehensive view of voice production mechanisms, overcoming the limitations of previous instruments and complementing traditional auditory assessments (Ghio et al., 2022).

Figure 2: EVA2 Station'

Applications of EVA2 in Phonetic Research

Ghio et al. (2023) note that EVA2 has been used in numerous phonetic studies, for example:

- For laboratory speech production analysis:

Meynadier, Ghio, Cesari-Lietard, & Robert (2019) developed a protocol for aerodynamic analysis of nasalization in French, addressing both regional varieties and clinical variations.

- For field speech production analysis, including linguistic research within the GDR “*Grand Rift Africain*”:

Carbone, Bouchet, Ghio, Legou, André, et al. (2022) created the *Speed-Vel Project*, a corpus of acoustic and aerodynamic data to measure droplet emission during speech interaction.

- For neurological analysis of Parkinsonian dysarthria:

Duez, Ghio, & Viallet (2020) studied the effect of linguistic context on the perception of consonants in Parkinsonian Read French speech.

3.3.3. Rothenberg Mask: Evolution and Acoustic Considerations

The Rothenberg mask, developed by Rothenberg (1973, 1977), is a central instrument in experimental phonetics for measuring airflow during vocal production. Its rigid design and geometry produce measurable acoustic effects, such as formant reduction. This is particularly noticeable in open vowels, like /a/, where the first two formants can decrease by 50 to 100 Hz due to the effective elongation of the vocal tract. However, these variations are relatively small (around 5%) and do not significantly compromise basic aerodynamic assessment.

Later versions, such as the OroNasal Mask (Figure 3), enabled important advances by allowing simultaneous measurement of oral and nasal airflow, as well as nasality (nasalance), defined as the proportion of nasal acoustic energy relative to the total (oral plus nasal) within approximately the first formant range of vowels (350–750 Hz). This measure has become a clinical reference for assessing oral-nasal resonator balance (Fletcher, 1978; Dalston et al., 1991; Hardin et al., 1992).

Recent research highlights the phenomenon of transpalatal nasality, i.e., the transfer of acoustic energy from the oral cavity to the nasal cavity via palatal structures, even when there is complete velopharyngeal closure. In speakers without cleft palate, up to 80% of nasality in voiced stop consonants (/b, d, g/) can be attributed to transpalatal effects, while about 20% results from acoustic crossover between microphones (Gildersleeve-Neumann & Dalston, 2001). Additionally, a positive, although non-significant, correlation has been observed between speaker fundamental frequency (F0) and nasality derived from both the first formant (F1) and F0, suggesting that the vibration of palatal structures partially depends on the acoustic energy generated by the voice.

From a clinical perspective, these findings are relevant: patients with repaired cleft palate may achieve complete velopharyngeal closure and still exhibit persistent oral-nasal imbalance due to the acoustic transmission characteristics of the soft palate (Gildersleeve-Neumann & Dalston, 2001; Rothenberg, 2006). This underscores the need to consider transpalatal nasality when interpreting airflow and resonance measurements in voice assessments and speech therapy.

Figure 3: EGG D800

Surgical masks have the disadvantage of being made from rigid plastic, necessary for some instruments such as pneumotachographs (PTG), which produce acoustic distortions. In the case of the EVA2 mask, although it is made of flexible silicone, this material acts as a low-pass filter, generating a pronounced resonance around 1400 Hz and an anti-resonance near 3500 Hz (Ghio & Teston, 2002; Elmerich, 2024). Consequently, audio recordings become less suitable for detailed acoustic analyses or perceptual experiments. Nasal funnels, in turn, partially block acoustic propagation and may be inadequate for certain morphologies, limiting their applicability (Elmerich, 2024).

The first-generation Rothenberg mask, due to its shape and rigidity, also causes acoustic alterations. For open vowels like /a/, the first two formants can decrease by 50 to 100 Hz due to the effective elongation of the vocal tract, although the overall reduction is small, about 5% (Rothenberg, 1973, 1977). Other studies report a spectral dip between 1600 and 2000 Hz, general attenuation above 1000 Hz, a slight peak around 1300 Hz, and another dip between 2000 and 2500 Hz (Hertegård & Gauffin, 1992; Badin et al., 1990).

To minimize these distortions, the Rothenberg mask was improved by incorporating openings on its surface, reducing acoustic resistance. The most recent version, known as the OroNasal Mask, is considered practically free of acoustic perturbations; the measured sounds are less distorted than in the first version, though not entirely distortion-free. Spectral trials using LPC analysis of the vowel /i/ pronounced by a French speaker, with different aerodynamic instruments, allowed a precise assessment of these differences (512-point window, 32 coefficients) (Elmerich, 2024).

4. Measurements and Analyses

4.1. Data Acquisition (EVA)

For the 54-word corpus recorded with the EVA system, any nasal airflow values below 0 were replaced with 0, as these were considered to result from inhalation caused by the large volume of air in the mask and thus not part of the speech production.

Data were acquired simultaneously across five synchronized channels: nasal airflow (NAF), oral airflow (OAF), electroglottographic (EGG) signals, laryngeal movement (LT), and an additional acoustic channel. Following the acquisition, all nasal airflow values below zero were set to zero, as these negative readings were assumed to result from inhalation caused by excess air in the mask and therefore did not reflect speech production. Manual segmentation of the data was performed in Praat (Boersma, 2001), with each phone annotated. (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Word [mèhã] 'sand'

4.2. Data Acquisition (EGG)

For the recordings of the 118- and 145-word lists, a D800 electroglottograph (Laryngograph) was used to acquire synchronized sound, electroglottographic (EGG), nasal, and oral airflow data. The EGG device was connected via USB to a laptop, and VoiceSuite 10.4.0 software (Laryngograph Ltd., 2021) was used for data collection. An omnidirectional microphone placed inside the Oronasal Teen-Adult mask from Glottal Enterprise captured the acoustic signal. The four

channels—audio, EGG, nasal, and oral airflow—were recorded at a sampling frequency of 24 kHz. Recordings took place in an enclosed space and during selected times to minimize background noise and environmental sounds from the Amazon rainforest, such as birdsong or other wildlife.

Data processing involved multiple steps: signals were downsampled to 4 kHz and filtered using a 50 Hz low-pass FIR filter. For each segment, the mean of the filtered signal was multiplied by the segment duration and scaled by the mask-specific D800 coefficients for nasal and oral airflow (coef_NF and coef_OF) provided by Laryngograph.

VoiceSuite 10.4.0 (Laryngograph Ltd, 2021) was used for the initial data collection. This software enables simultaneous recording of four channels: the acoustic signal (blue), electroglottography (EGG; green), nasal airflow (red), and oral airflow (black). It also allows calibration of the Glottal Enterprise oro-nasal mask for subsequent use (see Figure 5)

Figure 5. VoiceSuite10.4.0

4.3. Data segmentation and analysis

Once the data is acquired, any nasal airflow below 0 has been replaced with 0, as it is assumed to result from the speaker's inhalation due to a large quantity of air in the mask. Therefore, this physiological process is not part of the observed productions. The data segmentation was done manually using the Praat software (Boersma, 2001) (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Data Segmentation

The first tier (phone) corresponds to segmentation by individual segments. The second tier, labeled CV, differentiates consonants and vowels with more detailed annotation, specifying the types of glottalization, both vocalic and consonantal, present in the corpus. The third tier (V) indicates the counting of vowels from left to right according to whether they occur in the first, second, or third position within the word.

The fourth tier (burst) includes segmentation of the voice onset time (VOT) for voiceless plosive consonants [p, t, k], as well as the identification of burst traces in nasal consonants—a point discussed further below and addressed in a previous publication (Vega Rodriguez et al., 2024). The fifth tier contains information and segmentation related to glottal sounds.

The sixth tier provides syllabic information. This syllabification was carried out in collaboration with the Korebaju community to determine the placement of glottalization within the syllable. As no consensus was reached, we distinguished between glottalized vowels and glottal consonants in syllable onset position.

The seventh tier pertains to tone, based both on the F0 contour and perceptual evaluation: an initial annotation was performed by the author, followed by a validation round conducted by two student interns who are native speakers of other languages (2023: Alireza and Xinjia), confirming the perceptual tone.

Finally, the last three tiers correspond to the transcription, the translation, and the repetition number of each word, respectively.

5. Statistical analyses

The response variables analyzed in this study are nasal airflow (NAF) and oral airflow (OAF). From these measures, a nasalization ratio (RATIO) is calculated as the proportion of nasal airflow relative to total airflow, defined as $(NAF / (NAF + OAF))$, following the metric introduced in Vega Rodriguez et al. (2024). This ratio provides a quantitative measure

of nasalization and will be used to evaluate phonetic differences between oral, nasal, and nasalized vowels.

Statistical analyses will be conducted using linear mixed-effects models, which allow the analysis of repeated measurements while accounting for variation across speakers and lexical items. Models will be fitted using the `lme` function from the `nlme` package in R (R Core Team, 2021).

For Wordlist A, the models will examine the effects of syllable position (initial vs. medial) and segment type (CV vs. NV) on nasal airflow measurements. Speaker and lexical item will be included as random effects in order to account for repeated observations across tokens and repetitions.

For Wordlists B and C, mixed-effects models will evaluate the influence of phonological context and sociolinguistic variables (dialectal variety, gender, and generation) on nasal airflow measurements. Speaker and lexical item will again be included as random effects to account for variability across participants and lexical items.

When significant effects are identified, post-hoc pairwise comparisons will be conducted using estimated marginal means implemented in the `emmeans` package (Amelot, 2004; Riordan, 2019; Hoole & Kroos, 2020), with appropriate correction for multiple comparisons.

In addition to inferential analyses, descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, and range) will be calculated for each corpus. Data visualization, including boxplots and density plots, will be used to inspect distributional patterns and identify potential outliers.

CRedit Author Statement

Jenifer Vega Rodriguez: Conceptualization, Investigation, Data Curation, Data Collection, Data Processing, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets analyzed in this study were collected previously during phonetic fieldwork conducted in 2021 and 2023. The present submission corresponds to a Stage 1 Registered Report that preregisters the analytical procedures to be applied to these existing datasets in the context of a reproducibility study.

The protocol package, including materials, instruments, analysis scripts, and the preregistered analysis plan, is available at Zenodo with a persistent identifier (DOI): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17496154>

The full datasets and any additional code and outputs will be deposited in an open-access repository at Stage 2 following completion of the analyses. The data will be made available to reviewers and editors as required.

AI Use Statement

The authors declare that no AI-assisted tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Ethics Statement

This study follows the GIPSA-lab - CNRS “Participation à la Recherche” procedure, and ethics approval has been granted by GIPSA-lab. No formal approval number is required for this study. All participants will provide written informed consent, and their data will be anonymized to ensure confidentiality.

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